

Appendix B

Codebook for data collection

Field Name	Description	Type	Format	Example
<i>Lev4: Report Description</i>				
report_ID	uniquely identifies a report	numeric, one digit	number	
r_author	Name of first author	string	author	Smith
r_year	publication year	numeric		2010
r_apal	long citation	string	full APA-style citation	
r_apas	short citation	string	author (year) APA-style in-text citation	Smith (2015)
<i>Lev3: Study description</i>				
study_ID	uniquely identifies a study; different study or experiment numbers required	numeric, two digits	number	
t_country	country of conduction; where was the sample taken?	string	country	Germany
t_year	year of conduction; decisive is the end date of the study	numeric	year	2011
t_information_socio_demographics	Is there information on similarities of the different groups included (socio-demographics)?	dummy	0 - No, 1 - Yes	1
t_menu_design	Was the nudge implemented in the menu?	dummy	1 - No, 1 - Yes	1
t_information_room	Was the nudge presented around the dining room? (e.g. posters; pop-ups at the table)	dummy	0 - No, 1 - Yes	1
t_information_desk	Was the nudge presented at the desk? (nudges inside of the menu that were displayed above the counter (e.g. McDonalds) are not counted twice)	dummy	0 - No, 1 - Yes	1
t_nudge_verbal_prompt	Was the nudge verbally prompted?	dummy	0 - No, 1 - Yes	1
<i>Lev2: Sample Description</i>				
sample_ID	uniquely identifies a sample	numeric, three digits	number	

s_targetpop	Type of target population	string	target population	2
s_meanage_overall	mean age overall	numeric	number	35.2
s_meanage_pre	mean age of pre-group	numeric	number	35.2
s_meanage_post	mean age of post-group	numeric	number	33.5
s_meanage_comment		string	text comment	
s_female_overall	share of females overall	numeric	percentage	0.22
s_female_pre	share of females in the pre-group	numeric	percentage	0.34
s_female_post	share of females in the post-group	numeric	percentage	0.65
s_education_overall	educational level	string	text comment	
s_vegetarians/vegans_pre	share of vegetarians/vegans in the pre-group	numeric	percentage	0.23
s_vegetarians/vegans_post	share of vegetarians/vegans in the post-group	numeric	percentage	0.22
s_setting_cateen_cafeteria	Did the study take place in a canteen/cafeteria?	dummy	0 - No, 1 - Yes	1
s_setting_restaurant	Did the study take place in a restaurant?	dummy	0 - No, 1 - Yes	1
s_setting_laboratory	Did the study take place in a laboratory, e.g. gastronomy laboratory, sensory rooms, real worlds labs or framed field experiment?	dummy	0 - No, 1 - Yes	1
<i>Levl: Outcomes</i>				
outcome_ID		numeric, four digits		
o_design	Is the outcome calculated as a pre-post measure (between a baseline and a post-intervention period) or between-subject design (direct comparison between two groups, one of which was an experimental condition that's been exposed to a nudge)	options	0 - PrePost, 1 - between subject	
o_mealtime		options	1 - breakfast, 2 - lunch, 3 - dinner, 4 - snack	1
o_mealtime_comment	For which mealtime? if not assignable to mealtime	string	text comment	
o_intervention_category	Which nudge category?	Options	1 - decision information, 2 - decision structure, 3 - decision assistance	

o_intervention_technique	Which type of nudge?	Options	1 - translate information, 2 - make information visible, 3 - provide social reference points, 4 - change choice defaults, 5 - change option related effort, 6 - change range or composition of options, 7 - change option consequences, 8 - provide reminders, 9 - facilitate commitment	2
o_intervention_comment	comments about the nudge; especially if there is a combined nudge	string	text comment	The study employed a combination of nudges 1/3 (category/technique), 2/4 and 3/7
o_intervention_check	Did the researches conduct an intervention check, to see if the nudge has been noted?	dummy	0 - No, 1 - Yes	if there is no explicit mentioning of any intervention check or similar behaviour the standard for this is 0
o_time_lag	In case of a pre-post design: How long was the time lag between baseline and intervention period? In case of a between-subject comparison this variable is always = 0; the minimum time lag for a pre-post design is 1.	numeric	number	2 (e.g. for a change in menu after the weekend); 0 in case of between-subject design; 1 in case of a nudge implementation from one day to the next; 365 = 1 year / same period of the previous year
o_time	How many days of intervention?	numeric	number	
o_share of vegetarian/vegan dishes_pre	Share of vegetarian/vegan main options in the pre-phase? Options don't need to be displayed in the menu.	numeric	percentage	
o_share of vegetarian/vegan dishes_post	Share of vegetarian/vegan main options in the post-phase? Options don't	numeric	percentage	

	need to be displayed in the menu.			
o_rebound_check	Did the study investigate a 3rd time period after intervention period 1, to look for possible rebound effects? Rebound meaning an increase in meat sales after a first nudging period.	dummy	0 - No, 1 - Yes	1
<i>Outcome measures for two-group comparisons (dichotomous - event counts - quantitative)</i>				
n.meat.pre_con	Number of meat dishes (fish not included) before the nudge intervention	numeric	number	
n.meat.post_exp	Number of meat dishes (fish not included) after the nudge intervention	numeric	number	
n.pre_con	Number of dishes served overall (meat, veg and fish) before the nudge intervention	numeric	number	
n.post_exp	Number of dishes served overall (meat, veg and fish) after the nudge intervention	numeric	number	
n_comment	Column to report any unusual things; especially if the data provided on meat contains other ingredients like fish that are not strictly meat	string	text comment	contains fish

Table S1*Socio demographics across samples (N = 51)*

Mean age	N	Gender distribution amongst diners	N
39.94	27	56 %	32

Note. Gender distribution is expressed female sided. k = outcomes reported with the respective demographic data.

Table S2*Distribution of target populations (N = 9) across samples (N = 51)*

Target populations	N	%
Adolescents	5	10
General population	15	29
Students and University Staff	21	41
Older people	5	10
Consumer regulation experts	1	2
Students and PhDs	1	2
Public health experts	1	2
Hospital visitors	1	2
Hospital staff	1	2

Note. A sample could only consist of one target population.

Table S3*Distribution of locations of interventions.*

Location	N	%
Canteen	27	53
Restaurant	20	39
Living lab	6	12

Note. A study could be assigned to more than 1 location.

Table S4

Distribution of outcomes (N = 84) across countries.

Country	N	%
Belgium	6	7.1
Denmark	9	10.7
France	6	7.1
Germany	5	6.0
Italy	2	2.4
Netherlands	5	6.0
Portugal	1	1.2
Sweden	15	17.9
Switzerland	1	1.2
United Kingdom	11	13.1
USA	23	27.4

Note: All countries are modern western countries.

Table S5

Distribution of outcomes (N = 84) across mealtimes.

Mealtime	N	%
Breakfast	0	0
Lunch	42	50.0
Dinner	9	10.7
Snack	2	2.4
NA	31	36.9

Note: Mealtimes were reported for 53 (63,1%) outcomes. Some of the outcomes (see NA) that are not included here reported no mealtime at all or set the intervention to include multiple mealtimes.

Table S6*Distribution of outcomes (N = 84) across nudging categories.*

Nudging category	N	%
Decision information	56	66.7
Decision structure	21	25.0
Decision assistance	6	07.1

Table S7*Distribution of outcomes (N = 84) across nudging techniques.*

Nudging technique	N	%
1. Translate information	0	
2. Make information visible	19	22.6
3. Social reference points	36	42.9
4. Change choice defaults	12	14.3
5. Change option related effort	0	
6. Change range or composition of options	9	10.7
7. Change option consequences	0	
8. Provide reminders	0	
9. Facilitate commitment	9	7.1

Note. No study in our collection included nudges of technique 1, 5, 7 and 8.

Table S8*Omnibus test of moderators*

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% CI		p
			LL	UL	
Mixed effects					
Technique 2	.0143	.0573	-.0980	.1266	.8026
Technique 3	-.0282	.0610	-.1478	.0914	.6442
Technique 4	-.5903	.1127	-.8112	-.3694	< .001
Technique 6	.0866	.0691	-.0489	.2221	.2102
Technique 9	-.0363	.0727	-.1788	.1062	.6177
Consumer regulation experts	-.1692	.1312	-.4262	.0879	.1971

General population	-.0576	.0635	-.1822	.0669	.3641
Hospital staff	-.1284	.0766	-.2785	.0217	.0935
Hospital visitors	.0028	.0764	-.1470	.1525	.9712
Older people	.0253	.0686	-.1091	.1579	.7124
Public health experts	-.2231	.1277	-.4734	.0273	.0807
Students and PhDs	-.1362	.1339	-.3988	.1263	.3091
Students and staff	-.0018	.0528	-.1053	.1017	.9729
Menu design	-.0342	.0299	-.0927	.0244	.2525
Technique 3 * General population	-.0212	.0382	-.0961	.0536	.5785
Technique 4 * General population	.2643	.1027	.0630	.4655	.0101
Technique 6 * General population	.0513	.0453	-.0375	.1401	.2574
Technique 3 * Menu design	.0553	.0486	-.0400	.1505	.2554
Technique 6 * Menu design	-.1156	.0567	-.2267	-.0044	.0416
General population * Menu design	.0708	.0446	-.0166	.1583	.1125
τ^2		.0019		.0021	.0080

Note. Number of outcomes $k = 80$. $Q_E(df = 60) = 3051.0240$; $p < .001$. $Q_M(df = 20) = 610.5664$, $p < .001$. CI = Confidence interval; LL = lower limit; UL = upper limit.